

1 RESEARCH ARTICLE

2 **Supplement file for *InSAR measurement of vertical land motion in***
3 ***New Zealand cities, and implications for sea-level rise projections***

4 J. R. Kearse^{a,b}, Tim Stern^a, Ian Hamling^c, Simon Lamb^a, and Sigrún Hreinsdóttir^c

5 ^aSchool of Geography, Environment and Earth Sciences, Victoria University of Wellington,
6 Wellington, New Zealand; ^bDepartment of Geophysics, Graduate School of Science, Kyoto
7 University, Japan; ^cGNS Science, Lower Hutt, New Zealand

8 **ARTICLE HISTORY**

9 Compiled February 18, 2025

10 **1. InSAR data**

11 Sentinel-1 InSAR data are provided by the European Space Agency, and accessed
12 through the Alaska Satellite Facility web portal <https://asf.alaska.edu> last accessed
13 13/02/2024. Single-Look Complex images (SLC) were downloaded for both ascend-
14 ing and descending orbits. Data continuity and coverage for descending tracks is only
15 available from 2018 onwards. To develop reliable VLM products, coverage of both as-
16 cending and descending orbits is required; we therefore limit the time period of this
17 study to approximately 3 years between 2018 and late 2021. Specific orbits, time pe-
18 riods, and number of images used for each of the study areas are listed in Table 1.
19 Image stacks were produced using ISCE2 *stackSentinel* software (Rosen et al. 2012),
20 where each SLC is coregistered to a common reference image geometry. The con-
21 tribution of topography is removed using the 30 m SRTM digital elevation model.
22 For time-series processing, the coregistered SLC stacks are first parsed to MiaplPy
23 software (<https://github.com/insarlab/MiaplPy>) for phase linking and interferogram
24 generation, SNAPHU software for interferogram unwrapping, and then to MintPy
25 software for (<https://github.com/insarlab/MintPy>) for unwrapping error corrections,
26 time-series corrections and velocity calculation. An example of the processing steps is
27 shown below for Dunedin.

28 **2. Selecting Distributed Scatterers (DS)**

29 For each pixel, MiaplPy searches within a 15 by 15 pixel neighbourhood in range
30 and azimuth, respectively, to identify pixels that share common amplitude and phase
31 statistics. A Coherence matrix is then determined using the self-similar pixel groupings
32 for the full network of images, and inverted for the wrapped phase time-series (Mirzaee
33 et al. 2023). Suitable DS candidates are selected from the resulting average temporal
34 coherence, above a threshold of 0.7. When applied to urban environments (Figure 1),
35 this process essentially screens for built environment ground cover, while excluding
36 natural ground cover that exhibits seasonal loss of coherence and falls below the 0.7

region	track	SLC images	period
Auckland	A81	88	20180809-20210724
Auckland	D146	88	20180807-20210815
South Auckland	A81	88	20180809-20210724
South Auckland	D146	88	20180807-20210815
Tauranga	A08	102	20180406-20210824
Tauranga	D73	100	20180404-20210822
Porirua	A08	93	20180615-20210810
Porirua	D73	88	20180615-20210530
Wellington	A08	93	20180615-20210810
Wellington	D73	88	20180615-20210530
Lower Hutt	A08	93	20180615-20210810
Lower Hutt	D73	88	20180615-20210530
Christchurch	A52	109	20180807-20220723
Christchurch	D146	90	20180807-20210827
Dunedin	A23	93	20180712-20210813
Dunedin	D73	95	20180807-20211014

Table 1. SAR acquisition information. For track column, "A" refers to ascending orbit, and "D" refers to descending orbit.

37 threshold. In addition, this process will screen for any changes in the built environment
38 over the period of the dataset; for example, any building construction or demolition
39 will result in a loss of temporal coherence.

Figure 1. Selection of candidate distributed scatterers (DS). (a) Google Earth image of Dunedin City. (b) Map of temporal coherence. Notice that the built environment provides a highly coherent surface suitable for time-series analysis. (c) Mask for DS candidates that exhibit a temporal coherence > 0.7 .

40 3. Interferogram Network Selection

41 To minimize the propagation of unwrapping errors, and to reduce the computational
42 burden, a single-reference network of interferograms is chosen (Figure 2). The refer-
43 ence date is selected to be a the center of the dataset, both in terms of time period

44 and perpendicular baseline length. Minimal loss of coherence over the longer tempo-
 45 ral baselines (maximum of 660 days in the Dunedin case) is afforded by the urban
 46 landscape. Phase unwrapping is performed by SNAPHU (Chen and Zebker 2001). Mi-
 47 aplPy’s automated phase-bridging method was applied to the unwrapped time-series
 48 to correct for unwrapping errors; however, no corrections were necessary. This is likely
 49 due to the high coherence and limited areal extent of the individual study areas. The
 50 unwrapped phase time-series is then parsed to MintPy software (Yunjun et al. 2019)
 51 for reference point selection, time-series inversion, and finally time-series correction.

Figure 2. Network of interferograms constructed using a single reference image: 2019-10-23.

52 4. Reference Point Selection and Time-Series Inversion

53 InSAR time-series and velocity products for each study area are relative to a single
 54 point within the scene. This study uses individual GNSS station vertical velocities
 55 to anchor each city-wide InSAR VLM map to the ITRF2014 reference frame. This
 56 is achieved by the addition of a static offset to the VLM maps that is equal to the
 57 vertical velocity measured by the GNSS sensor. Therefore, reference point selection is
 58 a critical user-defined step in the processing workflow.

59 Many of the urban coastal strips in this study contain GNSS stations within high-
 60 coherence areas, such as Auckland City (AUKT), Lower Hutt (AVLN), Wellington City
 61 (WGTN), and Dunedin (OUSD). For these regions we use the location of the GNSS
 62 stations as the point of reference, and the same point is selected for both ascending
 63 and descending tracks. For other urban coastal strips, where nearby GNSS stations lie
 64 outside of the high-coherence built environment, including Tauranga (TRNG), Porirua
 65 (PAEK), and Christchurch (YALD), and for South Auckland where the nearest GNSS
 66 station is within Auckland City (AUKT), reference points were selected based on the
 67 geological and topographic conditions of the GNSS site, in order minimize differential
 68 VLM between the reference point and the GNSS sensor. Site specific detail is provided
 69 for each coastal strip in the main text.

Figure 3. InSAR data for Dunedin City (ascending a-c; descending d-f). (a) Map of velocity in mm/yr, (b) map of velocity uncertainty (standard deviation) in mm/yr, (c) time-series for selected points ts1 (light grey), and ts2 (dark grey). Note the larger uncertainties in ascending track velocity at points ts1 and ts2 (see panel (b)), which are a function of the larger spread in the displacement time-series about the mean rate (see panel (c)), when compared to the descending track.

70 For each pixel, the unwrapped phase time-series is converted to range-change (in
 71 meters) and an average velocity is calculated using least squares inversion. Equation
 72 (10) from Fattahi and Amelung (2015) is used to calculate the formal uncertainties in
 73 the pixel by pixel velocity estimation (σ_v), which are equal to the standard deviation
 74 of the displacement time-series residuals:

$$\sigma_v = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (d_i - \hat{d}_i)^2}{(N - 2) \sum_{i=1}^N (t_i - \bar{t})^2}} \quad (1)$$

75 where N is the number of images in the time-series, and d_i, \hat{d}_i are the real and
 76 predicted displacements. To illustrate the velocity calculation step, Figure 3c displays
 77 the displacement time-series at two locations within Dunedin City (ts1 and ts2), from
 78 which the velocities shown in Figure 3a are calculated. Larger uncertainties in the
 79 velocity for the ascending data at locations ts1 and ts2 (Figure 3b) are due to the larger
 80 standard deviation in the displacement time-series (Figure 3c), when compared to the
 81 descending track which exhibits a tighter distribution of displacement measurements
 82 about the mean rate (Figure 3f). LOS velocities and associated uncertainties for all
 83 cities in this study are available in the supporting information.

84 To mitigate any regional biases from atmospheric delay, a linear ramp is estimated
 85 and subtracted from each image in the stack before velocity calculation. However, this
 86 contributed little to the final LOS velocity; for example, across Dunedin City a ramp
 87 of approximately 0.01 mm/year/km was applied.

88 To assess whether a 3-year time-series of InSAR observations is sufficient to obtain a
 89 velocity measurement, an approximately 8-year time-series is produced for the Dunedin
 90 urban area. This time-series contains $N = 205$ SAR images between January 2015 and
 91 December 2022. $N - 1$ individual linear velocities are calculated (as described above) by
 92 increasing the time-series incrementally, beginning with just two images. In this way,
 93 subsequent images in the stack are included, with the final calculation containing all
 94 images in the stack. Figure 4 shows the difference in velocity estimation as a function
 95 of increasing length of time-series, from less than 1 year, to the full ~ 8 years. By 3
 96 years, the differences between the calculated velocities is small < 1 mm/yr, suggesting
 97 that velocities are above the noise floor.

Figure 4. Plot showing velocity calculated with incremental increases in the length of the time-series.

98 **5. Vertical Land Motion Calculation**

99 In preparation for LOS decomposition into vertical and horizontal components, LOS
 100 velocity images for both ascending and descending tracks (e.g., Figures 3a and 3d) are
 101 resampled and clipped to the same grid with a pixel spacing of 10 m. Figure ?? shows
 102 the VLM results for Dunedin City. Velocities are relative to the reference point (labeled
 103 'ref OUSD'), and do not contain any long-wavelength tectonic vertical deformation.
 104 Instead they highlight any LLS occurring within the urban coastal strip.

105 To characterise VLM and LLS more accurately, the vertical velocity of a GNSS
 106 station within the footprint of the InSAR data (which, in the case of Dunedin is co-
 107 located with the reference point), or a nearby GNSS stations is added to the InSAR-
 108 derived VLM velocity (Figure 3b).

109 Uncertainties in VLM rate at each InSAR measurement point are equal to the
 110 sum of the formal uncertainties for both tracks (e.g. see Equation 1). However, this
 111 does not capture the additional uncertainty associated with the arbitrary choice of
 112 reference point. To capture the uncertainty associated with the arbitrary selection of
 113 the reference point, we compute the standard deviation of VLM values within a 500
 114 m grid centered on the chosen reference point. Figure ?? in the main text shows the
 115 distribution of VLM measurements within the 500 m window surrounding the reference
 116 point in Dunedin. The standard deviation of these measurements is 0.71 mm/year. The
 117 light blue shading in Figure ?? represents $\pm 1\sigma$.

118 The total uncertainty in VLM for each InSAR measurement point (U_{VLM}) is equal
 119 to

$$U_{VLM} = \sqrt{U_{insar}^2 + U_{ref}^2 + U_{GNSS}^2} \quad (2)$$

120 where U_{insar} is the sum of formal uncertainties in the LOS velocity for both ascend-
 121 ing and descending tracks, U_{ref} is the uncertainty associated with the reference point
 122 selection, and U_{GNSS} is the uncertainty in the vertical GNSS velocity. below are the
 123 maps of uncertainty in VLM.

124 For Porirua, where GNSS station PAEK is located 10 km northeast of the urban
 125 district, it is not clear whether the VLM at the chosen reference point will be the
 126 same as that measured by PAEK. Although the spatial limitations of the InSAR data
 127 prevent us from making this assessment directly, we compare the VLM rates for the
 128 reference point at Porirua with VLM data from Hamling et al. (2022), which is based
 129 on 2003-2011 Envisat InSAR data. Hamling et al. (2022) tie their InSAR data to
 130 the available GNSS data in the area (including PAEK). Figure 5 shows the VLM data
 131 from (Hamling et al. 2022) between Porirua and PAEK; at the location of the reference
 132 point (blue) both datasets measure a VLM of -1.1 mm/yr, which suggests that the
 133 selected reference point is appropriate to tie the InSAR data to PAEK.

134 For Christchurch, GNSS station YALD is chosen to tie the InSAR data, due to
 135 its proximity (5 km) from the urban district, and its location on Holocene gravel
 136 deposits, similar to much of the Christchurch urban areas. Other GNSS stations in
 137 the area include MQZG and LYTT. LYTT has data available before 2019 and so it
 138 not used. MQZG is located at larger distance (15 km) from the urban district, and is
 139 located on elevated volcanic bedrock. The time-series of vertical displacement for both
 140 MQZG and YALD is displayed below in Figure 6 and shows that both stations are
 141 measuring similar vertical deformation for the time period since YALD was installed.

Figure 5. Profile of VLM between Porirua and GNSS station PAEK. The InSAR data of Hamling et al. (2022) are shown in grey. At the location of the reference point for Porirua in this study (blue), both data are in agreement, showing that a VLM of -1.1 for the reference location is appropriate.

Figure 6. Time-series of vertical displacement for GNSS sensors YALD and MQZG. These data demonstrate that the vertical deformation of both YALD and MQZG are not significantly different since 2014 when YALD was installed. Data are download from GeoNet FITS data service.

Figure 7. (a) Map of VLM uncertainty for Dunedin. (c) Histogram of VLM uncertainty.

Figure 8. (a) Map of VLM uncertainty for Christchurch. (c) Histogram of VLM uncertainty.

Figure 9. (a) Map of VLM uncertainty for Wellington. (c) Histogram of VLM uncertainty.

Figure 10. (a) Map of VLM uncertainty for Lower Hutt. (c) Histogram of VLM uncertainty.

Figure 11. (a) Map of VLM uncertainty for Porirua. (c) Histogram of VLM uncertainty.

Figure 12. (a) Map of VLM uncertainty for Tauranga. (c) Histogram of VLM uncertainty.

Figure 13. (a) Map of VLM uncertainty for South Auckland. (c) Histogram of VLM uncertainty.

Figure 14. (a) Map of VLM uncertainty for Auckland. (c) Histogram of VLM uncertainty.

142 **6. Time-series of vertical displacement and offset corrections for GNSS**
 143 **stations**

144 We used Hector software to estimate linear velocities and their formal uncertainties
 145 (Bos et al. 2013). When calculating velocities and uncertainties, Hector takes into
 146 consideration the time-correlated noise, the bias introduced by annual periodic com-
 147 ponent of the time-series, and the estimated magnitude of each of the offsets in the
 148 time-series. Figure 15 shows the uncorrected vertical displacement time-series for all
 149 4 stations processed in this study. To demonstrate that the HECTOR model displace-
 150 ment is a good fit to the data, we present the de-trended time-series in Figure 16, which
 151 is calculated by subtracting the modeled time-series components from the uncorrected
 152 time-series.

153 **References**

154 Bos M, Fernandes R, Williams S, Bastos L. 2013. Fast error analysis of continuous gnss ob-
 155 servations with missing data. *Journal of Geodesy*. 87(4):351–360.
 156 Chen CW, Zebker HA. 2001. Two-dimensional phase unwrapping with use of statistical models
 157 for cost functions in nonlinear optimization. *JOSA A*. 18(2):338–351.
 158 Fattahi H, Amelung F. 2015. Insar bias and uncertainty due to the systematic and stochastic
 159 tropospheric delay. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*. 120(12):8758–8773.
 160 Hamling IJ, Wright TJ, Hreinsdóttir S, Wallace LM. 2022. A snapshot of new zealand’s dy-
 161 namic deformation field from envisat insar and gnss observations between 2003 and 2011.
 162 *Geophysical Research Letters*. 49(2):e2021GL096465.
 163 Mirzaee S, Amelung F, Fattahi H. 2023. Non-linear phase linking using joined distributed and
 164 persistent scatterers. *Computers & geosciences*. 171:105291.
 165 Rosen PA, Gurrola E, Sacco GF, Zebker H. 2012. The insar scientific computing environment.
 166 In: *EUSAR 2012; 9th European conference on synthetic aperture radar*. VDE. p. 730–733.
 167 Yunjun Z, Fattahi H, Amelung F. 2019. Small baseline insar time series analysis: Unwrapping
 168 error correction and noise reduction. *Computers & Geosciences*. 133:104331.

Figure 15. Raw GNSS solution timeseries for each GNSS station processed in this study. Offsets due to antenna changes and regional earthquake displacements are visible.

Figure 16. Detrended GNSS vertical position timeseries. These data were calculated by subtracting the modeled timeseries performed by Hector software from the uncorrected solutions.